

Oxy-fuel combustion and carbon capture: concepts, applications and potentials in industry and power generation

Opening Keynote

IFRF TOTeM 52 "Oxy-Fuel Combustion and CCUS"

Jörg Leicher, May 27, 2026, Essen, Germany

Oxy-fuel combustion and CCUS – not exactly new topics for IFRF

TOTeM #	Location	Topic	Year
8	Loughborough (UK)	High temperature combustion – High air preheat/oxygen enrichment	1993
17	Cernay-la-Ville (France)	The Use of Oxygen for Industrial Combustion	2002
26	Birmingham (UK)	CO ₂ control, capture, sequestration, storage and emissions trading	2003
31	Pisa (Italy)	Oxy-combustion technologies and applications	2008
39	Pisa (Italy)	Oxy-coal Combustion	2013
41	Warsaw (Poland)	Optimisation of OXY/COAL/FGR systems – state of the art for scaling and modelling	2014
52	Essen (Germany)	Oxy-fuel combustion and CCUS	2026

Energy is essential for our modern world...

Primary energy demand in TWh/a

Data source: Energy Institute - Statistical Review of World Energy (2025); Smil (2017) - |
Note: In the absence of more recent data, traditional biomass is assumed constant since 2015.
OurWorldinData.org/energy | CC BY

Source: Our World in Data, 2025

Energy is essential for our modern world... but it's also a growing problem

Primary energy demand in TWh/a

Data source: Energy Institute - Statistical Review of World Energy (2025); Smil (2017) - |
Note: In the absence of more recent data, traditional biomass is assumed constant since 2015.
OurWorldinData.org/energy | CC BY

Source: Our World in Data, 2025

Global annual CO₂ emissions in 10⁹ t/a

Data source: Global Carbon Budget (2025)

OurWorldinData.org/co2-and-greenhouse-gas-emissions | CC BY

Source: Global Carbon Project / Our World in Data

It's no accident that these curves look almost identical!

Almost all human activities involve GHG emissions today...

Global GHG emissions by sector (2023)

Electricity & Heat: 33.6 %

Transportation: 14.3 %

Agriculture: 12.3 %

Manufacturing & Construction: 12.2 %
(energy only)

Source: Climate Watch, World Resources Institute

... but not all GHG emissions are directly linked to energy

Non-energy related emissions by sector (2023) Non-energy related industrial emissions (2023)

LULUCF: 0.9%

Source: Climate Watch, World Resources Institute

LULUCF: Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry

Industrial process emissions

Non-energy related industrial emissions (2023)

Source: Climate Watch, World Resources Institute

Shares of energy and process CO₂ emissions in selected industries (2020)

Source: IEA (2020)

Pathways to reduce global GHG emissions

IEA World Energy Outlook 2019

Total

Industry

Reducing GHG emissions is a challenge that will require a variety of different solutions. Electrification (with renewable energies or even nuclear) alone is not going to cut it.

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How do oxy-fuel combustion and carbon capture, utilization and storage (CCUS) fit into this picture?

Let's start with oxy-fuel combustion...

IEA World Energy Outlook 2019

Industry

Oxy-fuel combustion can be a means to:

- improve energy efficiency

Let's start with oxy-fuel combustion...

IEA World Energy Outlook 2019

Industry

Oxy-fuel combustion can be a means to:

- improve energy efficiency
- use alternative fuels

Let's start with oxy-fuel combustion...

IEA World Energy Outlook 2019

Oxy-fuel combustion can be a means to:

- improve energy efficiency
- use alternative fuels
- **make CCUS easier**

There are actually **two kinds of oxy-fuel combustion**:

- „**classic**“ oxy-fuel (air is substituted by pure oxygen, often with a gaseous fuel)
- „**diluted**“ oxy-fuel (air is substituted by a mix of O₂ and recycled flue gas, often with a solid fuel)

„Classic“ oxy-fuel combustion

Oxy-fuel combustion in thermal processing industries

- Oxy-fuel combustion is **state-of-the-art** in energy-intensive industries to **improve thermal efficiency in high-temperature** combustion processes.
- It is also used to **boost productivity** and to **reduce NO_x emissions** today. In the chemical industry, it may also serve to dispose of hazardous materials.
- **Flame temperatures are extremely high**, and the high concentrations of CO₂ and H₂O in the flue gas drastically **enhance radiative heat transfer**.
- The **cost of O₂ generation** has to be taken into account as well, however.

Oxy-fuel combustion and efficiency in thermal processing

Image: C.E. Baukal Jr., Industrial Burners Handbook, CRC Press, 2003

Image: von Schéele, J., Carlsson, A., Jonsson, M., Frank, E., Adendorff, M., New Oxyfuel Technology for Energy-Efficient and Ultra-Low NOx Annealing of Steel, INFUB 13, Albufeira, Portugal, 2022

Oxy-fuel combustion and alternative fuels

Natural gas / hydrogen blends (up to 100 % H₂)

Ammonia

100% Natural gas - oxyfuel

100% Ammonia - oxyfuel

Source: TU Graz / Messer (Project HyDreams)

Source: Nippon Sanso

Source: GWI

Oxy-fuel combustion and NO_x: examples from experiments for the glass industry

■ preheated air (1150 °C)

P = 500 kW; $\lambda = 1.1$

T_{furnace} ≈ 1600 °C

■ oxy-fuel

P = 320 kW; $\lambda = 1.05$

T_{furnace} ≈ 1600 °C

Source: GWI
(projects HyGlass & COSIMa)

Ways to further improve energy efficiency in oxy-fuel combustion

Combined fuel / O₂ preheating

Image: Air Liquide

Thermo-Chemical Regeneration (TCR)

Image: Linde / Nippon Sanso

„Diluted“ oxy-fuel combustion with recycled flue gas

Oxy-fuel combustion comes in two flavors: „diluted“ oxy-fuel

- There is a different motivation to use oxy-fuel combustion in **thermal power generation** (and some **manufacturing industries**): it is intended to **make CO₂ capture easier** in CCUS.
- For these applications, a different kind of oxy-fuel may be applied to facilitate CO₂ removal from the flue gas. Air is substituted with a **blend of O₂ and recycled flue gas**. Thus, the flue gas consists only of CO₂, H₂O (and some leftover O₂). CO₂ can easily be separated from the flue gas by condensing the water vapor. **There will likely be an efficiency penalty, however.**
- This idea originated in the power plant sector to „decarbonize“ coal-fired power generation. In the manufacturing sector, this concept is particularly interesting for industries with significant **process-related emissions of CO₂**, e.g. cement and lime, as they will likely need CCUS to deal with their GHG emissions.

Combustion with air, oxy-fuel combustion and CCUS

Combustion with air and CCU

Combustion with air, oxy-fuel combustion and CCUS

Combustion with air and CCU

Combustion with air, oxy-fuel combustion and CCUS

Combustion with air and CCU

CH₄ combustion with air ($\lambda = 1$)

species:	unit	wet flue
CO ₂	vol.-%	9.50
H ₂ O	vol.-%	19.00
O ₂	vol.-%	0.00
N ₂	vol.-%	71.49
T _{ad}	°C	1,982

Oxy-fuel combustion and CCU

Combustion with air, oxy-fuel combustion and CCUS

Combustion with air and CCU

Oxy-fuel combustion and CCU

Timeline of oxy-fuel demo plants for power generation

Source: Zheng, C., Liu, Z. (Eds.), Oxy-fuel Combustion - Fundamentals, Theory and Practice, 2018

New developments in power generation: Allam cycle with supercritical CO₂

Source: Net Power

Demo site (La Porte, Texas): 50 MW_{th}, in operation since 2018
net efficiency 58.9 % (LHV, including air separation unit)
pressure: up to 300 bar

CCUS – Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage

CCUS: Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage

- CCUS has actually been around for quite some time:
 - small scale: submarines, spacecraft, ...
 - **industrial scale**: enhanced oil recovery, natural gas processing, biogas upgrading, ...
- CCUS is an interesting option to decarbonize **hard-to-abate sectors**, e.g.:
 - industries with **significant process emissions of CO₂** (e.g. cement or lime)
 - waste-to-energy plants
 - „**blue**“ hydrogen production (SMR + CCS)
 - ...

Oxy-fuel is **not a requirement for CCUS...**
but it can help!

Theoretical minimum and actual energy demand for carbon capture

Energy to capture a tonne of CO₂

Source: James, B., Energy Fundamentals of Carbon Capture, 2023

Source: Wilcox, J., Carbon Capture, Springer-Verlag, 2012

Heidelberg Cement Brevik Carbon Capture Plant: first commercial CCS plant in the cement industry

- Operating since June 2025
- Target: approx. 400,000 t_{CO2}/a (45 % of site's emissions)
- >80 % of funding from Norwegian government

Heidelberg Cement Brevik Carbon Capture Plant: first commercial CCS plant in the cement industry

Image: Heidelberg Cements

LONGSHIP

The Brevik CCS project uses conventional post-combustion CCS. Similar projects are underway in Poland (Go4EcoPlanet) and France (K6 Program). A cement-related project with oxy-fuel combustion (GeZero) is planned to go operational in Geseke (Germany) in early 2029.

- (45 % of site's emissions)
- >80 % of funding from Norwegian government

BECCS: Bio Energy Carbon Capture and Storage

Image: D. Venton PNAS 2016;113:47:13260-13262

- In combination with biogenic fuels, CCUS can result in **negative emissions**.
- BECCU could become even more interesting as a **climate-neutral source for biogenic carbon**, e.g. for the production of **synthetic hydrocarbons** (chemical industry, SAF, plastics, ...)

DACCS: Direct Air Carbon Capture and Storage

- DACCS is considered as a way to decouple CCS from large emission point-sources of CO₂ such as power plants or industrial sites. Instead, CO₂ is removed from ambient air.
- Due to the low concentration of CO₂ in air, the energy demand for CO₂ removal is significant.
- Thus, a significant surplus of renewable energy is required.

Energy to capture a tonne of CO₂

Source: James, B., Energy Fundamentals of Carbon Capture, 2023

DACCS: Direct Air Carbon Capture and Storage

Image: Google Maps

Image: Climeworks

The plant went into operation in Hellisheiði, Iceland, in May 2024. Current data indicates that the actual amount of captured CO₂ is far below the nameplate capacity at the moment.

DACCS plant „Mammoth“
in Iceland (36,000 t CO₂/a planned)
This would be equivalent to the emissions of
about 8,000 cars in a year.

But is there still a use case for CCUS?

The relevance of CCUS is being challenged

Contribution of fossil fuels with CCUS to global energy supply in IEA's WEO NZE Scenario 2021 to 2025

Source: IEEFA compilation from International Energy Agency, World Energy Outlook, 2021-2025.

IEEFA

Institute for Energy Economics and Financial Analysis (2026):

„In the WEO 2025, the IEA assigns almost no role for CCUS in electric power generation in its NZE Scenario. CCUS in the 2050 setting accounts for just 1.2% of global energy generation, [...].

Including hard-to-abate industry effluents, CCUS is expected to contribute less than 5% of offset emissions by 2050. These projections underscore that CCUS is clearly a marginal technology and far from being on equal footing with renewable energy technologies.”

IEA World Energy Outlook 2025: Key performance figures for „clean“ energy technologies

Technology deployment has been uneven: some areas are tracking ahead of or in line with a path towards 1.5 °C, while others are lagging

Note: GW = gigawatt; Mt CO₂ = million tonnes of carbon dioxide.

Source: World Energy Outlook 2025, IEA, 2025

Among the clean energy technologies, CCUS is growing far more sluggishly than forecast, especially in comparison to other decarbonized power generation technologies such as wind and solar.

Current and planned global CO₂ capture capacities (IEA)

Capacities of current and planned large-scale CO₂ capture projects vs. the Net Zero Scenario, 2020-2030

IEA. Licence: CC BY 4.0

- Operating
- Under construction
- Advanced development
- Concept and feasibility
- Gap to NZE

Current and planned capture capacities by sector

Source: IEA CCUS Projects Explorer

EU policy targets and ambition gaps: GIE study

Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions

In mil. t CO₂ eq. | EU-Countries in EU Emission Trading System| Core Scenario

- Net Emissions
- ◊ Emission targets
- Others
- Energy Sector
- Transformation
- Internat. Transport
- Buildings
- Transport
- Industry
- LULUCF

LULUCF: Land use, land use-change and forestry
 DACCS: Direct air capture and storage,
 BECCS: Bioenergy carbon capture and storage

Source: Guminski, A., Kigle, S., Unlocking Energy System Efficiency: The Strategic Role of Hydrogen Infrastructure in Sector Coupling, GIE Sector Coupling Workshop, Brussels, Belgium, 2026

Sankey diagrams of predicted energy flows in the UK in 2050

[b) 2050 energy system

Source: The Seventh Carbon Budget – Advice for the UK Government, Climate Change Committee, 2025

Conclusion

- Oxy-fuel combustion and CCUS comprise a range of different technologies, sometimes with different purposes. Some of them are already well-established, others are still in the early phases of industrial-scale deployment.
- While **oxy-fuel combustion** will almost certainly play a role in the decarbonization of thermal processing industries (especially in combination with **new fuels** such as H_2), there is **no consensus how much CCUS is actually needed**, especially in power generation.
DACCS in particular seems problematic, given its high specific energy demand.
- There can – however – be an additional, potentially even **more important long-term purpose for CCU**, especially in combination with biogenic fuels... as a **source for climate-neutral carbon** for the chemical industry, sustainable aviation fuels and other applications where hydrocarbons will still be needed.

Thank you for your attention

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